

Development of metal (Ni)/ nitride (W₂N) nanocomposite film for industrial application

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Abstract

The nanocomposite (nc) coatings have been developed very recently. These coatings show greater mechanical properties, which is mainly due to small grain sizes (10nm). The nc coatings are composed of at least two or more individual phases. A significant number of other nanocomposite coatings have also been studied. The hardness reaches a maximum when the nanocrystals of the metal nitrides are covered with one monolayer (amorphous or metallic phase). With the incorporation of metallic phase, it can give the high harness and it also gives the high toughness. Therefore, in this work W₂N/Ni nc coatings were deposited on Si (100) substrate, using DC/RF reactive magnetron Co-sputtering by varying the Ni power (0W-50W). Well-grown structures were observed in FESEM images of *nc*-W₂NN/i coating. The mechanical property of these films improves with Ni power up to 10W The best hardness (35.64 GPa), elastic modulus (250.46 Gpa) was achieved at 10W Ni target power.

Fig: shows the nanocomposite structure of W₂N/Ni and its inset show the EDAX spectra which confirm the presence of W& Ni.

Keywords: Thin film, Nanocomposite, Hardness, magnetron sputtering.

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